

Non-Linear Ultrasonic Monitoring of Damage Progression in Disparate Rocks

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ABSTRACT

It is a well-established fact that the ultimate failure of rocks is preceded by the initiation, growth, and coalescence of micro-cracks. This paper focusses on non-destructive characterization of stress-induced damage progression in three types of rocks by experimentally capturing the elasto-dynamic non-linear response of the rocks, with the hypothesis that non-linear approaches have increased sensitivity relative to linear ultrasonic testing approaches. For this task, a non-linear ultrasonic testing procedure known as the Scaling Subtraction Method (SSM) has been implemented on uniaxially loaded rock specimens. The SSM procedure is based on exciting the damaged medium with two acoustic signals at different amplitudes consecutively. The linearly rescaled acoustic response at low excitation is subtracted from the response at large amplitude excitation for quantification of the elastic non-linearity of the medium by a non-linear indicator θ . At first, aluminum, Lyons sandstone, granodiorite and Gosford sandstone specimens were characterized using SSM and their inherent non-linearity was quantified. After this, the rock specimens were loaded under uniaxial compressive step-loading and ultrasonic measurements were performed simultaneously at each loading step. The non-linear indicator θ was calculated as the specimens were progressively damaged, and the changes in the non-linear response were linked to the different physical processes accompanying damage progression in rocks. The study concluded that the non-linear SSM technique is capable of sensitively recording signatures of the different stages of damage evolution in rocks.

KEYWORDS

Scaling Subtraction Method, Non-linear behavior, Damage, Crack Initiation, Rocks

1. INTRODUCTION

Numerous critical structures, like dams, bridges, tunnels, caverns, nuclear waste repositories, have been constructed with rocks being the ultimate load bearing structures. During the design life of these structures, rocks are generally subjected to anisotropic stresses (mechanical, thermal, chemical or seismic) which can lead to formation, growth and coalescence of micro-cracks eventually causing a degradation in the rock's strength.^{1,2,3,4,5} As a result, the life span of these structures is compromised, putting the involved life and property at risk. Therefore, it is important to consider the effect of micro-damage induced strength degradation in the engineering design and put in-place an efficient monitoring plan. Consequently, it is imperative to develop techniques through which one can monitor early damage manifestations in rocks, and at the same time understand the damage processes associated with micro-structure in rocks.^{6,7} Non-linear ultrasonic testing (NLUT) techniques have shown a great potential in detecting low level of damage in a wide spectrum of materials ranging from synthetic rocks (e.g. concrete and mortar) to rocks.⁸ In this study a variant of NLUT technique - the Scaling Subtraction Method (SSM) - has been used to evaluate its potential in detecting the signatures of different stages of micro-cracking in uniaxially loaded rock specimens.

Linear ultrasonic testing (LUT) is a more traditional approach for non-destructive characterization of damage in materials. LUT probes the changes in the linear acoustic wave parameters (i.e. pulse velocity, amplitude attenuation, and frequency shifts) as damage accumulates in a material.⁹ The linear theory of ultrasonic wave propagation is based on the assumption that the pulse velocity in a medium is constant, and the density and elasticity of a medium is independent of the transmitting wave amplitude.¹⁰ Theoretically, the first assumption implies that an ultrasonic wave will not be distorted as it propagates through a medium, although its amplitude might reduce due to scattering of the acoustic energy; that is why amplitude is a more sensitive parameter for capturing signatures of damage in a medium.^{11;12;13;14;15} Although wave attenuation is a fairly sensitive parameter for monitoring damage in a material, the changes of wave amplitude can be insignificant at low crack densities.^{8;16} Also, it has been documented that the signatures of damage evaluated using LUT methods are sensitive towards the fundamental frequency of the transducers used.¹⁷ As such, LUT methods may fail to allow for clear identification of low to moderate levels of damage in a material,^{18;19;20} which is crucial for understanding the onset of damage in rocks.

Studies have shown that non-destructive techniques that have the potential to extract the elasto-dynamic non-linear response of a material have broad implications in the non-destructive evaluation of materials.^{7; 21;22} NLUT approaches specifically capture the non-linear response signatures, which are originated in geomaterials particularly due to the presence of inhomogeneous features, like micro-cracks, grain boundaries, joints, debonding, delamination, crystal lattice defects, etc. NLUT has the distinct advantage

that it is extremely sensitive towards micro-damage as compared to LUT.^{7;16;18;23;24;25} NLUT technique analyses the interaction of ultrasonic waves with the material, and, specifically characterizes the non-linear effects such as: (i) super and sub-harmonic generations using the Finite Amplitude technique (FA), which requires very precise acoustic measurements^{10;15;26}; (ii) distortion in the resonance frequencies and wave attenuation with changes in excitation amplitudes using Non-linear Resonant Ultrasound Spectroscopy (NRUS)^{27;28}; (iii) wave mixing interactions using Non-linear Wave Modulation Spectroscopy (NWMS)⁷; and (iv) changes in the ultrasonic times-of-flight using a frequency mixing procedure known as the Dynamic Acousto-Elastic Technique (DAET).^{4;5;29;30;31} These techniques quantify the non-linear material behavior by using several non-linear material parameters.^{4;29;32} In the same group of damage detection techniques exploiting the non-linear features of the elastic response lies the Scaling Subtraction Method (SSM).^{33;34;35;36;37} SSM was proposed to overcome some issues affecting the more traditional NLUT damage detection techniques (for details, refer to,^{7;24}). The most significant issue affecting NLUT methods is the low signal to noise ratio at moderate levels of damage, which, decays rapidly on moving away from the source of non-linearity, therefore requiring very precise measurements.^{7;33} The benefit of SSM lies in the fact that the amplitude of the acquired non-linear signals is large enough to be easily distinguishable from the background noise. (4) The NLUT-SSM approach has also been found to be effective in detecting presence of localized damage in composite materials,³⁷ without the need of localizing transducers close to the source of non-linearity (defects) in the materials. (2) Furthermore, Antonaci et al.³⁶ compared the sensitivity of the LUT measurements against that of NLUT-SSM measurements for detecting damage progression in concrete, and concluded that NLUT-SSM is more effective than the traditional LUT measurements in that it can detect the distinction between initial stages of degradation and late damage propagation. As such, SSM has been previously used to identify damage in concrete and composite plates, but the effectiveness of SSM technique for detecting the presence of micro-cracking related damage in rocks has not yet been assessed.

Therefore, in the present paper, the NLUT-SSM has been tested to assess its potential for characterizing the damage processes in rocks with primary focus on the early level damage. Three rock types, Lyons sandstone (LS), granodiorite (G) and Gosford sandstone (GS) were tested for this purpose. An attempt is also made to characterize the difference in the observed non-linearity of the three rocks based on their micro-structure. The structure of the paper begins with a brief introduction on the fundamentals of non-linear ultrasonics. Next, the SSM technique has been described, followed by the testing procedure, and, then the results and conclusions are presented.

2. FUNDAMENTALS

2.1 Non-Linear Constitutive Model

The non-linearity in a material's characteristic behavior can be understood from three perspectives⁷: (i) the continuum mechanics perspective, where the constitutive laws relating stress-strain deviate from the Hooke's law;³⁸ (ii) the wave equation perspective, where the non-linear parameters are directly related to the observations appearing in ultrasonics; and (iii) the micro-mechanics perspective, where physical and phenomenological models are postulated so as to explain the observed non-linearity from perspectives (i) and (ii). Since, the definite explanation of the mechanistic origins of non-linearity is still being researched,⁷ here the mathematical description of non-linearity is described based on principles of continuum mechanics.

For an elastic material, the weakly non-linear elastic theory considers a Taylor series expansion of the elastic energy function in strain powers^{32;39;40; 41} :

$$W(E) = \frac{\lambda}{2} (\text{tr}E)^2 + \mu \text{tr}(E^2) + \frac{A'}{3} (\text{tr}E^3) + B' (\text{tr}E) \text{tr}(E^2) + \frac{C'}{3} (\text{tr}E)^3 \quad (1)$$

Equation 1 is an expansion for strain energy (W) with up to third order terms in strain powers, where: λ, μ are the Lamé's constants, tr denotes trace of matrix, E is Lagrangian strain tensor and A', B', C' are the Landau's third-order elastic constants.³² The second Piola-Kirchoff stress S_{II} can be obtained in terms of Lagrangian strain E through Equations 2 and 3:

$$S_{II} = \frac{\partial W(E)}{\partial E} \quad (2)$$

$$S_{II} = \lambda \text{tr}(E) I + 2\mu E + A' (\text{tr}(E))^2 I + B' (\text{tr}E^2) I + 2B' (\text{tr}E) E + C' E^2 \quad (3)$$

The Lagrangian strain E is computed from the displacement gradient D as per Equations 4 and 5, where X denotes the Lagrangian coordinates of the material points in the reference configuration⁴⁰:

$$D = \frac{\partial u_i(X,t)}{\partial X_j} \quad (4)$$

$$E = \frac{1}{2} (D + D^T + D^T D) \quad (5)$$

S_{II} can be expressed in terms of its argument D as per Equation (6):

$$S_{II}(D) = \frac{\lambda}{2} \text{tr}(D + D^T) I + \mu (D + D^T) + \frac{\lambda}{2} \text{tr}(DD^T) I + A' (\text{tr}(D))^2 I + \mu DD^T + B' \text{tr}(D) (D + D^T) + \frac{B'}{2} \text{tr}(D^2 + D^T D) I + \frac{C'}{4} (D^2 + (D^T)^2 + D^T D + DD^T) \quad (6)$$

Using Equation 6, the stress tensor S_{II} can be decomposed into its linear and non-linear parts, given in Equations 7 to 9:

$$S_{II}(\mathbf{D}) = S_{II}^L(\mathbf{D}) + S_{II}^{NL}(\mathbf{D}) \quad (7)$$

$$S_{II}^L(\mathbf{D}) = \frac{\lambda}{2} \text{tr}(\mathbf{D} + \mathbf{D}^T) \mathbf{I} + \mu (\mathbf{D} + \mathbf{D}^T) \quad (8)$$

$$S_{II}^{NL}(\mathbf{D}) = \frac{\lambda}{2} \text{tr}(\mathbf{D}\mathbf{D}^T) \mathbf{I} + A' (\text{tr}(\mathbf{D}))^2 \mathbf{I} + \mu \mathbf{D}\mathbf{D}^T \quad (9)$$

$$+ B' \text{tr}(\mathbf{D})(\mathbf{D} + \mathbf{D}^T) + \frac{B'}{2} \text{tr}(\mathbf{D}^2 + \mathbf{D}^T\mathbf{D}) \mathbf{I} + \frac{C'}{4} (\mathbf{D}^2 + (\mathbf{D}^T)^2 + \mathbf{D}^T\mathbf{D} + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{D}^T)$$

The second Piola-Kirchoff stress S_{II} can be related with the first Piola-Kirchoff stress S_I through the deformation gradient $E^* = I + E$, by $S_I = E^* \cdot (S_{II})$, i.e.

$$S_I(E^*) = S_I^L(E^*) + S_I^{NL}(E^*) \quad (10)$$

For defining the geometric non-linear effects under small strains (acoustic waves) in an ideal material obeying Hooke's law, the often neglected term $(\mathbf{D}^T\mathbf{D})$ should be considered in the description of the material constitutive laws represented by Equation 10.^{7;41;42} However, the non-linear mechanical behavior described by this continuum-based theory of elasticity is only capable of exhibiting classical non-linear anharmonic effects arising from atomic scale forces.⁴³ It has been demonstrated that the non-linearity explained through this classical approach is not capable of quantitatively predicting observations in a wide class of consolidated materials like soil, cement, rocks, etc.^{28;44} The compliant structural elements present in these kinds of materials tend to mask the classical atomic-molecular interactions and lead to hysteresis and memory features in the stress-strain relationship.^{10;45} These materials therefore tend to exhibit a discontinuous relationship between elastic properties and strain (unlike Equation 10), and are non-classical non-linear materials. Different models can be used for predicting non-classical non-linearity which ultimately has an effect on the material constitutive laws.^{46;47} In 1999, Guyer and Johnson gave a non-analytic term (modified to Z in this paper) by assuming a different expansion of the constitutive law,²¹ which could describe the contribution of the non-classical hysteretic elastic elements, simplified in Equation 11⁷:

$$S_I(E^*) = [S_I^L(E^*) + S_I^{NL}(E^*)] + Z \left[E^*, \dot{E}^* \right] \quad (11)$$

Given the material constitutive law (Equation 11), the one dimensional wave equations, for solids manifesting classical and non-classical behavior, can be obtained by using the principle of dynamic equilibrium⁷:

$$\rho \left(E_{1,tt}^* \right) = S_{11,x} + f(x,t) \quad (12)$$

where, ρ is the material density and f defines the source excitation.³⁴ The non-linear contributions in the material constitutive behavior as defined through Equations 11 and 12 tend to break the proportionality between the material response and the source excitation. From Equation 12, it is noticeable that the non-linear contributions in the response will rise if the source energy pulsed in the material is large and vice-versa.⁴⁸ The increased non-linear contributions at high source excitation violates the linearity-based superposition principle, and this phenomenon is exploited by the SSM technique.³⁴

2.2 Scaling Subtraction Method (SSM)

The idea behind SSM is that the non-linear contributions in the response begins to appear only when a sufficient amount of energy is imparted to a material.^{34;48} For a pure pulse excitation with an amplitude (A) and frequency (ω_o), the transmitted signal ($v(t)$) across a material medium can be expressed in terms of Fourier expansion^{33;34;35;36}:

$$v(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} B_n(A) \cos \left[n\omega_o t + \phi_n(A) \right] \quad (13)$$

The response amplitude $B_n(A)$ is governed by attenuation, dispersion and diffraction due to the granular micro-structure of the consolidated materials.¹⁰ Under a small pulse excitation amplitude (A_{low}), although a non-linear component of the wave response will exist (Equations 11, 12), it will be insignificant.^{34;48} Consequently, the response at small amplitudes tends to replicate that of a linear or intact specimen, and the signal can be regarded as a linear signal ($v_{lin}(t)$):

$$v_{low}(t) = B_1(A_{low} \rightarrow 0) \cos \left[\omega_o t + \phi_o \right] = v_{lin}(t) \quad (14)$$

Considering the dynamic response at low excitations to be linear, the linear response at sufficiently high pulse excitation with a scaled amplitude of $A_{high} = k \times A_{low}$ can be predicted using the linear superposition principle using the scale factor k :

$$v_{ref}(t) = k \cdot v_{lin}(t) = k \cdot B_1(A_{low} \rightarrow 0) \cos \left[\omega_o t + \phi_o \right] \quad (15)$$

The linear response at high input excitations can be considered as the response of an equivalent linear system.³⁷ At the same time, the actual response of the material $v_{high}(t)$ at high input excitation (A_{high}) will include non-linear signal contributions and the relationship between the signals would be:

$$v_{ref}(t) = k \cdot v_{lin}(t) \neq v_{high}(t) \quad (16)$$

The deviation of the recorded signal from the linear reference signal represented by Equation 16 is exploited by the SSM technique for quantifying damage and inherent elasto-dynamic non-linear response of a material.^{34;35;36;48} SSM implements the extraction of the non-linear response through the application of a scaled subtracted signal $v_{ss}(t)$:

$$v_{ss}(t) = v_{ref}(t) - v_{high}(t) \quad (17)$$

The SS signal can be expressed in the form of Equation 18 using Equations 14 to 17:

$$v_{ss}(t) = k \cdot B_1(A_{p,lin}) \cos[\omega_o t + \phi_o] - B_1(A_p) \cos[\omega_o t + \phi_1(A_p)] - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} B_n(A_p) \cos[n\omega_o t + \phi_n(A_p)] \quad (18)$$

Except for noise effects, the scale subtracted signal will be negligible for non-damaged and linear materials (perfectly linear behavior), while it will increase with increasing amounts of material non-linearity and damage.³⁷ In principle, the classical non-linear Landau parameters can be estimated by the analyses of the SS signals,³⁴ however, this subject is not explored further in this paper because the non-linearity studied here is of the rock samples that exhibit non-classical non-linear behavior.²¹

In laboratory applications, the SSM can be implemented in 3 steps: (i) first, the response of the specimen for a small amplitude excitation is recorded; (ii) a scaled amplitude high voltage excitation is consecutively applied to the specimen and the response is recorded; (iii) the difference between the linear reference signal and the recorded signal is analyzed. The non-linear content of the response can be quantified through the total SSM indicator θ which represents the energy of the SSM signal and is calculated based on the area under the time-domain SSM signals^{34;49}:

$$\theta = \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \left[0.5(A_{SS,i} + A_{SS,i+1}) \right]^2 \cdot \Delta t \quad (19)$$

Here, $N=10000$ is the number of samples that corresponds to a sampling time of 10 μ s for the response of the material with the sampling rate of 1 Giga-samples per second, A_{ss} is the amplitude of the SS signal ($v_{ss}(t)$) and Δt is the interval between two sample points. θ as calculated in the present work is normalized with respect to Δt , because it is constant throughout the testing scheme. As shown in Equation 19, SSM is relatively robust given that the non-linear signature is derived by a simple subtraction method and doesn't

require the introduction of mathematical parameters (e.g. time-window length, paddings and etc.³⁴) involved in filtering procedures for the analysis of the sub and super-harmonic wave components.

3. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

3.1 Materials

This study on characterization and detection of processes associated with the progressive deformation in rocks was performed using three types of rocks: Lyons sandstone (LS), granodiorite (G), and Gosford sandstone (GS) (Fig. 1). The Lyons sandstone was obtained from Lyons, Colorado, which is in the front range of the Colorado Rocky Mountains (United States). It is aeolian in origin and was formed through long term consolidation of fine-grained quartz sand dunes.⁵⁰⁻⁵¹ Because of this, Lyons sandstone is primarily composed of quartz (85-90%) with some presence of clay minerals (10-12%)⁵² and is not very porous (porosity of about 4%). Lyons sandstone has previously been found to have an average grain size of about 190 μm .^{52;53} Because of its quartz-dominated mineralogy and its uniform fine-grained texture, the Lyons sandstone is both strong and brittle. The crystalline granodiorite rock specimens had grain sizes typically varying between 3-5 mm with a bulk density of 2766 kg/m^3 .⁵⁴ It consists of quartz (45-48%), plagioclase-feldspar (35-40%), biotite-mica (13-16%) and finely disseminated iron oxides (2-3%).⁵⁵ The Gosford sandstone is a unit within the massive (290 m thick) Triassic Hawkesbury sandstone of the Sydney Basin on the east coast of New South Wales. Using an X-ray CT scan, the porosity of the Gosford sandstone was estimated to be between 18.5% and 20%,^{56;57} and the average solid density was calculated to be 2226.5 kg/m^3 .^{58;59} X-ray diffraction analysis of Gosford sandstone showed that it is comprised of quartz (86%), illite (7%), kaolinite (6%) and anatase (1%).⁶⁰ The maximum grain size was estimated as 600 μm using the sieve analysis method.⁶¹ Four cores (1, 2, 3, 4) of each rock type were prepared by drilling, and the specimens were surface grounded to within 0.01 mm under dry conditions using mechanized grinding. All the prepared specimens were geometrically similar with a length to diameter ratio of approximately 2.25, and the diameters are shown in Fig. 1.

3.2 Testing Method

Of the four specimens prepared for each rock, the first specimen was tested under monotonic uniaxial compressive loading, and conventional strain parameters, such as axial strain, radial strain and crack volumetric strain, were determined for the purpose of studying the damage evolution.^{51;62} For the other three specimens (2, 3, 4), the damage evolution was monitored using the NLUT-SSM approach. The specimens were damaged monotonically by applying a quasi-static compressive load along their axial dimension for damage characterization through the conventional strain-based approach. A computer-controlled servo-hydraulic loading machine by Controls Group Inc. was used to uniaxially load the specimens in axial displacement feedback by advancing a piston against the specimen at a rate of 1 $\mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$ (Fig. 2(a)).

Parametric information such as load and strain was acquired using a chain extensometer and linear variable differential transformers (LVDT). The strain measurements helped in characterization of the internal damage processes in the rocks using the traditional approach which involves tracking of the stress-strain changes. The onset of cracking (termed as crack initiation, CI) was determined using the method given by Ghazvinian in 2015,⁶² in which the CI is defined as the stress corresponding to the point of inflection in the crack volumetric strain curve. The beginning of the crack propagation (termed as crack damage, CD) was estimated based on the estimation of stress corresponding to the onset of relaxation in the elastic modulus of the rock as calculated through the tangent modulus curve.^{63;64;65;66}

The non-linear ultrasonic SSM measurements on the specimens (2, 3, and 4) of each of the rock type were performed using the equipment shown in Fig. 2. Two identical piezoelectric longitudinal wave transducers (V-103) from Olympus NDT, Inc with a central frequency of 1 MHz and element diameter of 13 mm were used in the study as the emitter and receiver of the ultrasonic waves (Fig. 2(a)).^{35;36;37;48;67} The use of 1 MHz central frequency facilitated clear transmission of the ultrasonic waves without compromising on the sensitivity of the waves towards defects in the rock medium. Honey was used as the coupling medium for reducing the effect of impedance mismatch at the contact area between the rock and transducers.^{68;69;70;71;72;73;74;75} Rubber bands were used to attach the sensors to the specimen. The sensor assembly and coupling process was systematized to ensure repeatability in the ultrasonic measurements.^{51;70}

The excitation to the emitting transducer was provided by two types of waveform generators: for low voltage excitation (1-20 V), the Agilent 3350B from Keysight, Inc was used, and for high voltage excitation (up to 400 V) a 5077PR from Olympus, NDT was used (Fig. 2b). The two waveform generators were calibrated and synced so as to output identical time-domain single cycle pulses at a frequency of 5 kHz. The input excitations to the emitting transducers were gradually increasing which helped in systematic acquisition of the transmitted signals. The transmitted ultrasonic pulses were acquired in real-time using the 9-bit Tektronix TDS 3014C DP oscilloscope (Fig. 2(b)). A Lab-view program was written to acquire the signals from the oscilloscope to the PC in real-time. The transmitted signals were acquired with a sampling frequency of 1 GHz which ensured a precise signal reconstruction based on Nyquist's theorem.^{35;36}

The NLUT-SSM technique was applied for understanding the behavior of the three disparate rocks (Fig. 1) in both their undamaged (intact) and damaged states. At first, an intact 2024 aluminum alloy specimen with similar dimensions as that of the rocks was used as an elastically linear standard material to calibrate the experimental set-up, and to quantitatively compare its non-linearity relative to the rocks.^{4;34;35;36;67} After this, the NLUT-SSM approach was employed for tracking the different stages of damage evolution in the rocks specimens. The rock specimens were damaged through uniaxial step-loading

at 1 $\mu\text{m/s}$, and periodically throughout the test, the strain level was held constant at each step to allow a series of ultrasonic measurements to be made. At each level of the step-load, the SSM approach described in Sec. 2.2 was implemented for quantifying the elasto-dynamic non-linear response of the specimens through the total SSM indicator θ .

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Undamaged Specimens

As introduced in Sec. 3, three types of rock (Lyons sandstone, Granodiorite, Gosford sandstone) and one metallic (aluminum) specimen in their intact (undamaged) state have been tested using SSM. Fig. 3 shows the reconstructed reference signal ($v_{\text{ref}}(t)$), high voltage non-linear signal ($v_{\text{non-lin}}(t)$) and the scale subtracted signal ($v_{\text{ss}}(t)$) for the specimens at similar levels of the transmitted voltages. The reference and non-linear signals are fairly similar for the aluminum specimen (Fig. 3a) while there is a marked difference in these signals for Lyons sandstone, granodiorite and Gosford sandstone (Fig. 3b, 3c, 3d). The distortion in the signals is associated with the sensitive phenomenon of non-linear attenuation of the waves and amplitude-dependent phase distortion of the recorded signals.^{33;34;35;36;76}

The 2024 aluminum alloy used here consists of about 93% aluminum by weight and has grain sizes varying between 0.41 μm to 20 μm .^{77;78;79;80} Aluminum has a high quality factor (Q-value) of about 150000 which implies no significant attenuation of the waves propagating through it.^{81;82;83} This behavior of aluminum can be attributed to its strong metallic bonding, negligible porosity and minimal impedance mismatch at its grain boundaries. Consequently, aluminum is weakly non-linear, further confirmed by the very low amplitude of the scale subtracted signal (Fig. 3a). In contrast, the three rocks show substantial amplitudes of the non-linear SS signals (Figs. 3b, 3c, 3d). This inhomogeneous behavior of the rocks is because of their complex micro-structure comprising of several compliant features.^{84;85} Sandstones (Lyons and Gosford), in particular are comprised of hard (Quartz) phases and soft phases (clays, cracks, grain boundaries, joints, etc.), in which the soft phase occupies a much smaller volume.⁸⁶ The hard phases, also termed as the ‘bricks’, are relatively insensitive to deformation while the soft phases (‘mortar’) are subjected to strong deformation, which is the fundamental origin of the non-linear response.^{22;87} In the case of the crystalline rock (granodiorite), the possible sources for the distortion of the received signals (Fig. 3c) can be: (i) the contrast in the density and the elastic properties of mineral phases; (ii) the grain-grain contact heterogeneity due to variable shape, size and behavior of the grains, and, due to the dislocations contained within individual crystals.^{4;22;31;67;88;89} Under low levels of dynamic strain, a longitudinal wave propagating through the soft phase will not face appreciable strain and the response can be presumed to be linear as the strain contrast between the hard and soft phases will not be significant, but at higher levels of dynamic

strains, the strain contrast between the two phases is significant, and, therefore the received signal gets attenuated and distorted (Figs. 3b, 3c, 3d).

The non-linear indicator (θ) was calculated as a measure of the energy of the SSM signals (Equation 19) and is shown in Fig. 4, which is the plot of θ versus the output amplitude of the transmitted signals for all the tested materials. (3) The reproducibility of the SSM non-linear indicator θ was ascertained by measuring the θ values a total of 3 times for each of the rock specimens. The variation in the θ values (shown in Fig. 4) as calculated through the acquired linear and non-linear signals (Fig. 3) for the rock specimens was 2-3%.

Fig. 4 shows marked increase in non-linear indicator θ as a function of output amplitude for the three rock specimens, in contrast to the aluminum specimen, which is characteristic of materials with marked non-linearity.³⁴ In particular, the non-linear indicator (θ) of the aluminum specimen is an order of magnitude smaller when compared with the non-linear indicators (θ) of the sandstones and granodiorite. It is a verification of the fact the aluminum and its alloys exhibit a very weak classical elastic non-linearity.^{4;67;85} The rock specimens, with high non-linear indicator (θ) values, are inherently much more non-linear and exhibit non-linear dependence of θ on the test voltage. Gosford sandstone has the maximum sensitivity to the test voltage, while the sensitivity of granodiorite falls between that of the two sandstones. It is important to note that the mechanisms associated with elastic non-linear behavior in most of the sandstones differ from that of the non-linear processes in crystalline rocks (granodiorites).^{4;67;31;90} The motion produced by a longitudinal-wave is an alternating compression and expansion of the material, which generates alternating compressive and tensile strains around the micro-structure. In case of sandstones, the alternating dynamic strains trigger material softening under both compressive and tensile strains. In comparison, material softening in granodiorites ensues only under tensile strains as the material hardens under compression.⁴ This softening effect in sandstones can be explained by the shear dominated slipping mechanism at the grain-cement interaction which is activated under both compressive and tensile strains, while, in case of granodiorites, the origin of non-linearity is the ‘clapping action’ of dynamic opening and closing of grain contacts.^{4;91} Following this, the non-linear behavior of the three rocks as observed in Fig. 4 can be explained.

Although both Gosford and Lyons sandstone have broadly similar mineralogical characteristics (i.e. they are primarily composed of quartz), the difference in the non-linearity of the two rocks can instead be attributed to the porosity of the two rocks and their cementation. Gosford sandstone is much more porous (soft phase) (18-20%), while Lyons sandstone has a much lower porosity (4-5%). Lyons sandstone has high uniaxial compressive strength (UCS) and is well-sorted (UCS=190 MPa and Young’s Modulus=45 GPa as stated by Thompson⁵⁰ in 1949 and Shirole et al.⁵¹ in 2017), whereas Gosford sandstone is a poorly cemented immature quartz sandstone, with a much lower UCS (40 MPa) and Young’s Modulus (15 GPa).^{59;92} Poor-

cementation and the presence of increased pore-space in Gosford sandstone may be the primary reason for the higher non-linear response (θ) of the Gosford sandstone as compared to the lower values of θ in Lyons sandstone. The high compressive strength of LS implies that its grain-cement interactions are less susceptible to shear-slip (softening), while the poor-cementation quality (as evidenced by the low UCS) in Gosford sandstone amplifies the shear-slip at the grain-cement contacts increasing its elasto-dynamic non-linearity (Fig. 4). The elastic non-linearity of intact granodiorite can be associated with internal grain-scale heterogeneity originating at the grain-contacts which are subjected to ‘clapping action’. The modulus of the hard phases present in granodiorite (plagioclase and quartz) is approximately 88-94 GPa and that of the soft phase (biotite-mica) is approximately 34 GPa.⁹³ The significant presence of the softer phase (biotite-mica) might have increased the impedance mismatch at the grain-contacts between the acoustically different minerals present in the granodiorite and therefore the ‘clapping action’ at the grain contacts. The dislocations contained within individual crystals (both soft and hard) can also be the reasons for the non-trivial non-linear elastic behavior of granodiorite. Although, it is difficult to compare the difference in the non-linearity of the crystalline granodiorite and the consolidated sandstones, overall the observations of intact material dynamic non-linearity produced by the SSM technique are satisfactory, as they are consistent with the findings of other studies which employed DAET for classification of elasto-dynamic non-linear behavior of disparate rocks.^{4:31:67;90:94} The quantification of non-linearity in intact specimens through the SSM indicator θ also facilitated the interpretation of the effect of inherent micro-structure of the rocks on its dynamic behavior.

4.2 Specimens under Uniaxial Compression

4.2.1 Strain-Based Damage Characterization Approach

As explained in Sec. 3.2, before proceeding with ultrasonic testing, the rock specimens were damaged in a quasi-static manner under monotonic loading. Fig. 5 shows the quasi-static loading curve of all the rock specimens, which is typical of the curve produced when the ultrasonic measurements were carried out on the specimen. The curves of axial strain (AS), radial strain (RS), crack volumetric strain (CS) and tangent modulus (TM) have been plotted against the percent failure strength (stress as a percentage of the UCS). The mechanistic behavior of the rock specimens as they experience damage under loading can be understood through these curves. Fig. 5 shows that the rock specimens undergo a compaction stage, up to about 15% of UCS, 20% of UCS and 30% of UCS for the LS, G and GS respectively. The compaction stage seen can be explained as the pore-collapse and hardening of the rock specimens to varying degrees.

This stage is followed by a period of linear behavior where the instantaneous modulus of the rocks remains fairly constant. Even though the overall material behavior is linear-elastic in this stage, intergranular micro-cracks nucleate in this stage, starting at the crack initiation stress (CI).⁶² Subsequent

axial softening of the material behavior marks the onset of macroscopic non-linearity in the material, originated through the coalescence of micro-cracks. This is termed as the crack damage (CD), and it is the stress threshold at which the micro-cracks in the rock begin to coalesce, ultimately leading to formation of a discrete failure plane at the peak strength.⁹⁵ CI and CD were calculated based on the conventional approach in which CI is the stress corresponding to the point of inflection in the crack volumetric strain curve, while CD corresponds to the onset of relaxation in the Young's Modulus of the rock as calculated through the tangent modulus curve. For LS and GS, the CD threshold was calculated at the stress where softening in the instantaneous tangent modulus of the rocks was observed (see Fig. 5a, c).^{63;64} The CD for granodiorite was calculated based on the local non-linearity in the axial strain-percent failure curve (inset of Fig. 5b). The estimated CI and CD thresholds for the three rocks are summarized in Table 1.

4.2.2 NLUT-SSM Approach

After the conventional testing of the rocks, the NLUT-SSM testing on three specimens (2, 3, and 4) of each rock type was conducted. The stages of damage progression in the three rock types as explained through the conventional stress-strain behavior in the three monotonically loaded rock specimens served as a benchmark for understanding the failure progression and assisted in interpretation of the NLUT-SSM observations. For analysis of the damage progression using SSM technique, the ultrasonic measurements were performed in the constant-strain time interval between one loading step and the following. Fig. 6, depicts the variation of the SSM non-linear indicator (θ) versus output amplitude at different stages of loading for the three specimens (2, 3 and 4) of each rock type (because LS shows least θ values among the three rocks, a different scale has been chosen in case of LS for clearly showing the variation in θ with output voltage at different stages of loading). The percentage loading shown in Fig. 6 (LS-2) varies by approximately $\pm 2.5\%$ relative to the values shown. Although the curves shown in Fig. 6 vary depending on the type of rock, it is fair to say that for all the specimens the non-linear indicator (θ) versus output amplitude shows a specific non-monotonic trend depending on the damage. Initially, the non-linear signal content shows a decrease in comparison to the non-linear content at the intact state (blue and red curves have lower magnitude of θ in comparison to the black curve). For Lyons sandstone (LS) and granodiorite (G), the reduction in non-linearity is observed for up to about 10-20% of the damage, while for Gosford sandstone (GS) it happens up to a damage of 30%-40% of the UCS. With further increase in the load (30%-65% of the UCS), θ progressively reverts back to the same value as that of the intact (undeformed) specimen (compare dark-brown, green and pink lines), and eventually surpasses it. With more damage (65-90% of UCS), the change in non-linear θ is more conspicuous and can be easily distinguished from the curves at lower damage levels (pink, yellow and dark-blue curves). The final ultrasonic measurement for specimens

G-4 and GS-4 was conducted at 80% of damage, and because of this, the non-linear curves at 90% of damage are missing from their data.

Damage (i.e. the presence of micro-cracks) is directly related to the increase in the non-linear content of the propagating ultrasonic waves with increasing load. The interpretation of the non-linear ultrasonic measurements and damage progression can be enhanced by monitoring the evolution of non-linear indicator θ with damage. For this, Fig. 7 shows the variation in non-linear indicator θ versus load level, where θ corresponds to the maximum output level of the transmitted signals. Fig. 7 shows that the changes in non-linear indicator θ with damage follows a specific trend, which particularly can be categorized into three stages, in accordance with the observations of Bruno et al. in 2009 and Antonaci et al. in 2010 who saw similar trend on mortar and concrete specimens respectively.^{34;35} Initially in stage I, which corresponds to low load levels (0-15%), a decrease in the non-linear signal content is observed. This is consistent with the increase in the slope of the stress-strain curve due to material hardening (Fig. 5). Studies have shown that during initial stages of compressive loading, a compaction phase is observed in rocks.^{96;97} Stage I is consistent with the rearrangement of the internal structure, with micro-defects closing and pores collapsing, causing an increase in the stiffness of the specimen. The sealing of pre-existing pores and micro-cracks, without formation of any new micro-cracks, is central to the reduction in the non-linearity of the specimens as shown by Fig. 7. Lyons sandstone, because of its low porosity and strong cementation, doesn't show a particularly pronounced stage I (Fig. 5a and Fig. 7), whereas this stage can be easily identified in the Gosford sandstone data, because it can be categorized as a loose and porous rock.^{59;98;99} Granodiorite also shows a substantial decrease in non-linearity during stage I, which may be attributed to the reduced non-linear dissipation at stiffened grain contacts at low levels of compressive loads. With a further increase in load, as observed in the crack-strain plot (Fig. 5), no new micro-cracks are formed between 10%-20% of load for Lyons sandstone and Granite, and, 10%-35% of the loading for Gosford sandstone. This is indicative of the perfectly linear-elastic behavior of the rocks, and is consistent with the fairly constant non-linear indicator in the same stress regime. At approximately 20% of the loading in case of LS and G, and 40% of the loading for GS, the non-linear indicator θ increases abruptly and distinctly to approximately the same level as that of the intact specimen (onset of Stage II). This distinct observation of the rise in non-linear content is consistent with the CI threshold estimated using the crack strain curve (Table 1). As the loading increases beyond the CI threshold, the SSM non-linearity continues to rise gradually except for G-3. Although, the axial-strain versus percent loading curve is linear in this region, the non-linearity in the radial strain curve (formation of isolated vertical cracks and reduction in radial stiffness) can explain the slight increase in non-linearity observed in stage II. This observation of increment of θ during stage II differs from the results of Bruno et al. (2009), where constant θ values were observed during stage II. The onset of stage III is associated with an abrupt increase in the rate at which non-linear θ rises, which occurs

approximately at 70%-80% of the UCS for all the rocks studied. This amplified increase in the non-linearity is consistent with the formation of trans-granular cracks and micro-crack coalescence at the CD threshold as determined by the conventional approach (Table 1). The formation of these cracks makes the macro-scale behavior of the specimens non-linear which is very distinctly reflected in the non-linear θ indicator. The distinct signatures of the changes in θ as damage progresses in the rock specimens is a testament of the fact that the NLUT-SSM technique is sensitive towards the detection of damage and failure progression in rocks; perhaps most important from a practical standpoint is the ability of NLUT-SSM to sensitively record low levels of damage (close to CI).

(2) For comparison of the sensitivity of the SSM using nonlinear ultrasonic testing with linear ultrasonic testing methods, amplitude, which is a linear attribute of the ultrasonic waves was monitored at various levels of damage. To this purpose, changes in the amplitude of the non-linear signals ($v_{\text{non-lin}}(t)$) obtained at the excitation voltage of 400 V were examined. Fig. 8 shows the changes in the amplitude with increasing levels of damage for rock specimens LS-4, G-3 and GS-3. The changes in amplitude are very gradual and subtle for LS and G, while for GS the amplitude is decreasing from the beginning of the loading. From the Fig. 8 it is conspicuous that the LUT attribute (amplitude) is incapable of sensitively capturing the signature of crack initiation (CI) for the rocks, as no significant change in amplitude could be observed in the initial stages of loading (0-40% of the UCS). At advanced level of damage (80-90% of UCS), an acute drop in the amplitude is visible but this drop in amplitude occurs at a stress which is above the CD stress threshold for the three rocks (Table 1). Also, with the changes in the amplitude it is difficult to monitor the signatures of the different stages of the progressive damage in the three rock specimens, in contrast to the NLUT-SSM non-linear indicator θ . These observations are consistent with the findings of Antonaci et al.³⁶ who concluded that NLUT-SSM is more efficient than traditional linear ultrasonic techniques in as much as it points out the distinction between initial stages of degradation and late damage propagation.

(1) In all the experiments performed in this study, the micro-cracks are expected to be aligned parallel to the direction of the uniaxial load,⁶² while the transducers are oriented perpendicular to this expected dominant micro-crack orientation (Fig. 2a). This orientation of the transducers enabled maximum interaction of the ultrasonic beam with the damage, which facilitated improved sensitivity of the NLUT-SSM measurements (θ) in detection of damage. Antonaci et al.³⁵ and Porcu et al.³⁷ studied the effect of the orientation of the transducers on the SSM non-linear indicator θ . They concluded that the sensitivity of θ to damage was only quantitatively effected by the orientation of the transducers with respect to the damage location, but that qualitatively, the SSM non-linear indicator θ was still capable of detecting damage irrespective of the transducer locations/orientations. Based on the general conclusions from these studies, the authors expect that changing the orientation of the transducers will lead to a general loss in the sensitivity

of SSM non-linear indicator θ towards damage, but still SSM non-linear indicator θ should be able to qualitatively differentiate between the stages of damage progression in rocks.

4.2.3 Comparison of Non-Linearity of the Rocks during the Progressive Damage Process

Section 4.1 showed that in the intact state, the Gosford sandstone specimens behaved in the most non-linear manner while the Lyons sandstone behaved in the least non-linear manner. In this section, the non-linear nature of these rocks has been compared as they are damaged under uniaxial compression. For the comparison of the non-linear behavior of the three rocks, a fixed output amplitude of 0.1 V was chosen for quantifying θ at each damage level. The 0.1 V was chosen as it was approximately equal to the maximum output voltage for the Gosford sandstone specimens (Fig. 5). The non-linear indicator θ at the output voltage of 0.1 V for each damage level and for each rock type was calculated by using a cubic polynomial curve fit on the non-linear indicator θ versus output-voltage curves shown in Fig. 5. This technique is similar to the procedure followed by Bruno et al. in 2009.³⁴ Subsequently, Fig. 9 is a scatter plot of the collected non-linear indicator θ values at increasing levels of damage for all three specimens of each rock type at a constant output level of 0.1 V. Through Fig. 9, it is reasonable to say that the absolute θ values of LS, G and GS specimens groups into three clusters respectively. The first cluster is that of the red-diamond markers with the lowest θ values, representing the test results of LS, the second cluster is that of G with black-circular markers with increased θ magnitude while the rest of the markers (blue-triangles) form the third cluster with the θ values representing GS. In addition, the best-fit polynomial curves for the non-linear θ values have also been depicted in Fig. 9, with the solid-red, solid-black and solid-blue lines representing LS, G and GS respectively. These trends, which show maximum non-linear behavior of GS and minimum of LS with G's behavior in-between of them are consistent with the discussion of section 4.1, implying that the characteristic non-linear behavior of the three rock types did not change significantly during the progressive damage process. The data fit curves also show that at the particular output amplitude, GS shows the maximum sensitivity for a change in non-linearity with increasing levels of damage. The susceptibility of LS towards changes in its non-linearity with damage is minimum while G's behavior falls in between of LS and GS. It follows the fact that since the inherent non-linearity of LS and G is fairly low in comparison to GS at the given excitation (Fig. 4), more energy is required to excite the damage (i.e. cracks) related non-linearities in the LS and G specimens. This observation is consistent with the hypothesis that non-linear contributions related to damage begin to appear only when the amount of energy transferred to the material reaches a certain threshold as per Equation 13.^{33,48} Accordingly, it is expected that the sensitivity of G's and LS's damage-related non-linear signatures will increase if the excitation energy is increased. This has already been corroborated in section 4.2.2, where the changes in non-linear θ values with damage have been found at the maximum output amplitudes.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The potential of the scaling subtraction method (SSM), which is a non-destructive non-linear ultrasonic measurement technique, for damage detection in rocks has been assessed in this paper. For this, three different specimens each of three different rock types (Lyons sandstone, granodiorite and Gosford sandstone) were acoustically insonified under different amplitudes, in both intact and damaged states. In their intact state, the SSM approach was able to characterize the inherent non-linearity associated with the three rock types. It was also capable of differentiating the weakly non-linear response of an aluminum specimen in comparison to the highly non-classical non-linear response of the three rocks. The intact GS showed stronger non-linear response in comparison to the LS and G. This difference was attributed to the variance in the micro-structures of these rocks, which greatly influences the mechanisms responsible for the elasto-dynamic non-linear behavior. The benefit from this is that the quantification of non-linearity in intact specimens through the SSM indicator θ can aid in an indirect non-destructive interpretation of the inherent micro-structure of the rocks or other materials.

(4)The NLUT-SSM approach is effective in detecting presence of localized damage in composite materials³⁷. The examination of the non-linear response of the rock specimens subjected to quasi-static loading helped in experimental validation of the sensitivity of the SSM to detect microcracking induced homogenous damage in the rocks. The findings revealed that the non-linear SSM technique is sensitive in capturing signatures of the different stages of damage evolution in the rocks. The results are fairly consistent with other studies which were carried out on concrete.^{33;34;35} A key attribute of the SSM θ indicator was found to be its sensitivity to record signatures of early damage manifestations. In particular, the θ indicator showed appreciable change at the stress level where micro-cracks started to develop (CI) in the rock specimens. The non-linear indicator θ was also very sensitive in detecting the formation of trans-granular cracks in the specimen (CD). When comparing the non-linear response under stress-induced damage for the three rocks at a particular output amplitude, it was found that GS is the most sensitive towards damage, while LS is the least sensitive. This is consistent with the inherent non-linear behavior of the two rocks under undamaged conditions. Finally, the method has proven to be very efficient in differentiating the three rocks, both in their intact state and damaged state.

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Table 1. CI and CD thresholds of the monotonically loaded rock specimens estimated through the conventional approach.

Rock Type	CI (% of the UCS)	CD (% of the UCS)	UCS (MPa)
Lyons sandstone (LS-1)	20-23	72-76	181
Granodiorite (G-1)	20-22	78-83	174
Gosford Sandstone (GS-1)	38-45	73-76	40

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Figure 1. The rock types used in the study. From left to right, Lyons sandstone (LS), granodiorite (G), and Gosford sandstone (GS) respectively.

Figure 2. (a) Typical UCS set-up in combination with the ultrasonic sensors, where: (a1) granodiorite specimen; (a2) chain extensometer; (a3) LVDT; (a4) emitting transducer; (a5) receiving transducer. (b) The experimental equipment used for the SSM ultrasonic measurements, where: (b1) oscilloscope and (b2) waveform generators.

Figure 3. Superposition of the linear reference signal (solid red line) on the high voltage non-linear signal (dotted black line). The SSM signal is also shown (solid blue line), which is the algebraic difference between reference and non-linear signal. (a) Aluminum; (b) Lyons sandstone; (c) Granodiorite; (d) Gosford sandstone.

Figure 4. Characterization of the different rocks and the aluminum through their non-linear signature by the application of SSM technique, where increasing output voltage implies increasing input excitation. Al denotes aluminum, LS denotes Lyons sandstone, G denotes granodiorite and GS denotes Gosford sandstone.

Figure 5. Stress-strain behavior under monotonic loading where, AS denotes axial strain, RS denotes radial strain, CS denotes crack strain and TM denotes tangent modulus. Plot also shows the CI and CD thresholds identified through the crack volumetric strain and instantaneous tangent modulus curves respectively.⁶² The plots are for: Lyons sandstone (LS-1); (b) Granodiorite (G-1); and (c) Gosford sandstone (GS-1). The inset in Fig. 5(b) is a magnification of the axial strain-percent failure plot and shows onset of non-linearity in G-1 due to localized deformation.

Figure 6. θ with output voltage at different levels of damage progression, where, the different color lines represent certain level of damage in the specimens (see LS-2). LS, G and GS stand in for Lyons sandstone, granodiorite and Gosford sandstone respectively, where 2, 3 and 4 are the specimen IDs.

Figure 7. Variation of the non-linear indicator θ with loading in linear scale for the rock specimens: GS-2, 3, 4; G-2, 3, 4 and LS-2, 3, 4. The non-linear indicator θ first decreases (Stage I), then rises at a gentle rate (Stage II), and with further loading increases drastically (Stage III).

Figure 8. The scatter plot of the non-linear θ values with damage of all the NLUT-SSM tests conducted on each type of the rock at a constant output amplitude of 0.1 V. The red-diamond markers, the black-circular markers, and the blue-triangular markers represent the SSM test results for all the specimens of Lyons sandstone (LS), granodiorite (G) and Gosford sandstone (GS) respectively. The red-solid line, black-solid line, and the dark-blue line highlights the best-fit for the non-linear θ values with damage for LS, G and GS.

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Fig. 7. Variation of the non-linear indicator θ with loading for the rock specimens: GS-2, 3, 4; G-2, 3, 4 and LS-2, 3, 4. The non-linear indicator θ first decreases (Stage I), then rises at a gentle rate (Stage II), and with further loading increases drastically (Stage III).

Fig. 8. The changes in the linear attribute of the ultrasonic waves (amplitude) with loading for the rock specimens LS-4, G-3 and GS-3. Similar observations were taken from other rock specimens.

Fig. 9. The scatter plot of the non-linear θ values with damage for all the NLUT-SSM tests conducted on each type of the rock at a constant output amplitude of 0.1 V. The red-diamond markers, the black-circular markers, and the blue-triangular markers represent the SSM test results for all the specimens of Lyons sandstone (LS), Granodiorite (G) and Gosford sandstone (GS) respectively. The red-solid line, black-solid line, and the dark-blue line highlights the best-fit for the non-linear θ values with damage for LS, G and GS.